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Synthesis of Substituted Phenols via Hydroxylation of Arenes Using Hydrogen Peroxide in the Presence of Hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium Triflate

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Abstract

A mild and efficient protocol for the synthesis of phenols from arenes has been developed using aqueous hydrogen peroxide as an oxidizing agent and hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium triflate as a promoter. The reactions were carried out with the simple procedure in EtOH-H₂O at room temperature in short reaction times.

Keywords: Substituted phenols, hexaphenyloxodiphosphonium triflate, hydroxylation, hydrogen peroxide, arene.